

Semi-Structured Interview Script and Questionnaire

Thank you for agreeing to participate in this interview for investigating the challenges facing adoption of blockchain technology that should ultimately help us to build a roadmap for software practitioners of blockchain projects:

As you already know, there is an emerging interest in this area of blockchain throughout the software profession. Your answers to the following questions will help us develop case example guidance for software development communities looking to explore integration problem of their best practices to blockchain projects. This interview should take around one hour and will be recorded so that we can more easily review the notes afterward. If at any point it would be helpful to refer us to project documents for additional information, please do so.

Information about people: their background, roles and reactions to the project.

1. Please tell me more about yourself and your role in the current project.
2. Are you involved in the requirement gathering process for a blockchain project? Have you ever been involved in a project concerned with decentralized development before?
3. Can you tell me about any situation where you observe an implementation of a bad/good practice ?

Practices of success

1. Which practices would you select to define best practices in blockchain development?
2. Have you found certain problems to be more difficult than others? If so, please elaborate on which ones are more helpful and why.
3. Were any practices unhelpful? If so, please elaborate on which ones were unhelpful and why.

Organizational Aspects

1. Could you indicate the problems encountered during organizational integration process? In which stages of software deployment do problems arise? Are there any organization-wise measures addressing these problems?
2. Did you encounter any problems that slow down the project either from the managerial part of the organization or due to the software development teams? If so, how did you resolve the encountered issues?
3. Did you perceive any advantages or disadvantages of the best practices you used after the deployment of the blockchain project?
4. How do you think we can tailor a software architecture to improve the productivity of blockchain project development?

(OPTIONAL, TIME-DEPENDENT)

Which factors do you think might affect the productivity of your blockchain project?

Are there any resources (e.g. documents, artifacts, etc.) your company has published that would help us further understand your efforts?

Finally, are there other practitioners we should talk to better understand your company's efforts to address blockchain issues through best practices?